

THE ROLE OF PUBLIC RELATIONS IN SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT AND ITS IMPACT ON SME GROWTH IN CALABAR

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ABSTRACT: The study examined the effect of supply chain public relations management practices on business performance of small and medium scale enterprises in Calabar, Cross River State. In the course of the study four hypotheses were formulated, data were collected from management staff of small and medium scale enterprises in Cross River State using structured questionnaire. The data were analysed utilizing inferential and descriptive statistics. Findings from the study revealed that the dimensions of Supply chain public relations management practices have a favourable and positive effect on small and medium scale enterprises in Calabar, Nigeria. On the basis of the findings, it was concluded that if supply chain public relations management practices activities are well implemented, there would be an improvement in business performance of small and medium scale enterprises. We recommended that supply chain public relations managers should develop strategies that will enhance their relationships with other stakeholders to improve on their business performance.

Keywords: Supply chain management, business performance, public relations management, medium and scale enterprises.

1.0

INTRODUCTION

Supply management according to Mpuon, Odigbo, Etuk & Usoro (2023b) and Zhang (2022) addressed strategic challenges like the integration of multiple business processes, the formation of strong ties between intermediaries, and the management of products and information as they commute across organizational and entrepreneurial frontiers. Mpuon, Etim, Offiong & Enouh (2021) and Onsongo et al. (2017) maintained that supply chain public relations practices help manufacturing firms to create and project a favourable corporate image of an organization by communicating the qualities of its

products and service to the public. Shamsan and Otieno (2015) and Mpuon, Etim, Etuk, Ejikeme (2023a) maintained that for an organization to have a favourable and rewarding corporate image, it has to effectively and efficiently engage in supply chain public relation management practices. In the assertion of Mpuon, Etim, Effa, Anna (2023b) and White, Vanc & Stafford (2010) supply chain public relations encourage effective business operations, mutual co-existence? According to and help business organization to promote the health and general wellbeing of its environments of operations. Festus (2014) and Mpuon, Etim, Arikpo, & Etuk (2022)

noted that there cannot be effective community relations without well-planned and articulate supply chain public relation management programmes. According to Huo, Han, Zhou, Wood & Zhao (2013) supply chain public relation management practice is a strategic communication process that builds mutually beneficial relationship between organizations and the public.

Similarly, Wu and Baah – Boakye (2009) and Mpuon (2018) stated that supply chain public relations management practices serve a variety of institutions in the society such as businesses, trade unions, government agencies, Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs), foundations, hospitals, schools, colleges and even religious institutions. Weirder and Holtzhausen (2009) and Mpuon (2019) argued that for this organizations to achieve their goals, they must develop effective supply chain relationship with a wide range of audiences and/or public such as employees, customers, immediate communities, shareholders, the society at large. While, Watson (2008) declared that in an ideal organization, supply chain public relations enable employee works harmoniously with their associates to achieve organizational goals and objectives, as opposed to achieving selfinterest. Although supply chain public relations management assumed modern status in the 20th century, it has certainly always been a way of life, hence as old as man. Its historical antecedents are traceable to Adam as observed by Aliede and Molokwu, (2015). Asemah (2011) argued that supply chain public relations management practice describes any form of communication by firms which is public, deliberately planned communication that concerns every organization whether commercial or non-

commercial as well as the government. Mpuon I. (2018a) maintained that supply chain public relations management strengthened organizations' needs to create a favourable image for itself before the generality of the public to ensure successful operation specifically in small and medium scale enterprise.

Supply chain public relations practices have been very vital to the survival of small and medium scale organizations in terms of effective and efficient business performance and operations Mpuon (2018b). Supply chain public relations management enhance small and medium scale enterprises multifaceted functions of evaluating attitude and executing actions, it examines suspicion and friction thereby providing bridges of understanding upon which goodwill reigns between an organization and the public that deals with it (Asemah, 2011; Mpuon, Essien, Efiom & Ita (2022). In the view of Aliede and Malokwu (2015) cited in Nwosu and Adomile (1992), supply chain public relations practices are means of winning friends, keeping them, doing good and getting rewards for it as well as being guided by public interest considerations of being socially responsible in order to be socially acceptable. Supply chain public relation practice is the art and science of supply chain actors achieving harmony with the environment through mutual understanding based on truth and full information (Mpuon , Efiom, Eko, Akaninyene & Eke, 2023; Nweke, 2001). British Institution of Public Relation (BIPR) asserted that supply chain public relation practice is a deliberated, planned and sustained effort aimed at enhancing business performance by establishing and maintaining mutual understanding between an organization and its public leading to customer satisfaction, profitability and

improved customer service (Aliede, 2015; Steers, 1991; Mpuon & Oyong, 2019).

In the view of Shamsan and Otieno (2015) most small and medium enterprises in Calabar, which engage in production on commercial scale view supply chain public relation practices as an expensive venture, perhaps forgetting the positive effects of how it will allow the public to view what the organization has to offer. The objectives and functions of supply chain public relations practices according to Nwasum (1996) involves the act of analyzing present trends and predicting their consequences, preventing and resolving conflicts, misconceptions, understanding and prejudices using communication to influence and mobilize public opinion and attitude for mutual benefit of the organizational management and the public. Eribaum (2002) opined that regardless of how effective companies may be, it will not make the desired impact if the public or final consumers are not versed with the company's business brand, successes and/or contributions. Jjuuko (2014) supported that supply chain public relations practices campaigns educate and informs people about an organization's abilities, enhances its brand recognition and makes it more alluring and relevant in the eyes of the public.

Thus, this study seeks to unravel the effect of supply chain public relations management practices on business performance of small and medium scale enterprises in Cross River State. Mpuon et al (2021) and Lattimore, Baskin & Heinman (2004) argued ignorance remains a major reason why companies are unable to appreciate the relevance of supply chain public relations management practices in sustaining their businesses. Rawjee (2012) asserted that it is only when a company fully understands the usefulness of a

particular strategy in keeping its mandate afloat that such a company will be able to key into the prospects of investing in such a strategy. Quite unfortunately, supply chain public relations management practices of small and medium scale enterprises have almost been relegated to the background in Cross River State. Conversely, where the controlling minds of a company are aware of the need to employ supply chain public relations mechanisms, they become lukewarm, lackadaisical, and lackluster in executing and implementing their moves towards engraining in sustainable supply chain public relations management activities. Thus, the statements of this research problem is to unveil the effects of event, news, speeches and public service activities on business performance of small and medium scale enterprises in Cross River State. The Practice of supply chain public relations in Nigeria as well as other parts of the world has been subjected to a barrage of wrong perceptions. White, Vanc & Stafford (2010) are of the view that some of the supply chain public relations practitioners themselves do not have a clear idea of what supply chain public relation actually entail. According to Daramola (2003) misconceptions trailing supply chain public relations include:

Courtesy: Some people erroneously view supply chain public relations as consisting of good manners or being polite or respectful to others. However, good manners alone do not constitute supply chain public relations neither does it independently guarantee a proper functionality of the tenets of supply chain public relations

Protocol: Even institutional officials erroneously believe that good supply chain public relations

practice is about protocol or the proper procedure of conducting official ceremonies.

Goodwill: Every organization or individual needs the cooperation of others to be able to achieve any mission or vision because no one is an island of himself thus goodwill alone is not enough.

Fine Appearance: Many people and corporate entities assume that supply chain public relations is equivalent to a fine appearance, an attractive face or glamorous outlook and for this reason alone, such people and institutions maintain a strict dress code or policy and nothing more.

Free Gift: Many company executives in Nigeria and indeed around the world believe in projecting their supply chain public relations as being charitable and benevolent through offer of free gifts such as Christmas hampers and Sallah rams. However efficient public relations practice does not necessarily begin and end with gratuitous gifts.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESES DEVELOPMENT

Supply chain public relations practices is the art and science of analyzing trends, predicting their consequences, counseling, organization, leadership and implementing planned programmes of action which will serve the interest of both organization and that of the public (Molleda & Alhassan, 2006, Fawcett, Walin, Allred, Fawcett, 2011, Mpuon & Oyong, 2019). This definition actually points out that supply chain public relations management practices have to do with the process of establishing and maintaining cordial relationship between an organization and the public so as to help the organization achieve its objectives (Uzoma, 2010; Mpuon et al., 2022a). Supply chain public relations management practices

is essentially about positively and systematically using actions and communications to influence people's attitudes, opinions, beliefs, interests and behaviour in given or desired direction (Murangwa, 2009; Mpuon (2018a, 2018b). For instance, Imevbore (2011) argued that adopting good environmental behaviour as well as building lasting credibility and reputation of individual and corporate entities like profit or nonprofit organization and even nations, states, local governments or communities called for a good supply chain public relations management practice. Nwusu & Uffoh (2006) Johnson & Zawari (2004) Mpuon, Eyo, & Kajang (20220) maintained that supply chain public relations management practices are the ethical and strategic management of communication and development of mutual relationships in order to build and improve on coalitions and policy, identify and manage issues and create message to achieve some outcomes within a socially responsible framework. Onsongo, Mberia & Jjuuko (2017) quoting the British Institute of Public Relation (BIPR), states that supply chain public relations management practices are deliberate planned that sustain organizations efforts to establish and maintain mutual understanding between other organization and its public. According to Samsup & Mehta et al. (2015) and Mpuon et al. (2023a, 2023b) supply chain public relation practice is a part of marketing communication strategy that enhanced an organization's message to its diverse public including customer, perspective investors, employees, suppliers, distributors, media journalist, social media networks, the government and the indeed the generality of the public. Furthermore, Peyronel et al. (2000) upheld that supply chain public relations

management practices is the practice of managing the flow of information between supply chain participants, suppliers, intermediaries, customers and organizations. Moreover, Huo et al. (2013) and Linda et al. (2002) argued that supply chain public relations management practices provide organizations the privilege of exposures to their audience using topics of public interest and news items that do not require direct payment Aliede (2015). Supply chain public relations consist of all forms of planned communication outward between a firm and its public for the purpose of achieving specific goals concerning mutual understanding (Uzoma, 2010). It is imperative to note therefore that supply chain public relations management practices are essential in achieving and sustaining corporate and social climate for harmonious co-existence and for enthroning sustainable image and reputation. (Nweke, 2001). Okafor and Malizu (2014) highlight the various branches and kinds of public relations to include; employee/labour, community, shareholder, government, media, corporate affairs, social / environmental and international relation. Aliede and Molokwo (2015) noted that the techniques and strategies of public relations practice include: transfer process model, race model, ten-point steps systematic model, four steps model, PCM or OP matrix model. Similarly, Daramola (2013), highlights the underlisted concepts of supply chain management practices as the common misconceptions of public relation viz; Courtesy, Protocol, Goodwill, Fine Appearance, According of Aliede and Molokwu (2015) the successful and effective implementation of any public relations programmes or campaign is never by chance nor luck. It is usually highly predictable because the

rightly taken methods, processes, technique and strategies are being used. Nweke (2001) submits that as a professional supply chain public relation practitioner, supply chain public relation personnel are needed from time to time to render public relation service required in solving problems facing their clients.

Good supply chain public relations encouraged employee relations which do not occur by accident. They are achieved by conscious supply chain relationships management design and deliberate effort to create them. Supply chain public relations strengthened good employee relations which are tangibly reflected in a good *es spirit de corps*, high standard of work performance and quality workmanship which in turn materially effects unit cost and profitability (Onwunali et al., 2006) According to Uzoma (2010) the supply chain public relations practitioner should endeavour to build employee confidence and trust through effective employee communication media, names, letters, buildings and printed speeches. He further explains that employee efficiency can be improved by recommending staff for refresher programmes.

According to Daramola (2003) supply chain public relations management practices facilitate community relations as planned activity to create a relationship of good neighbourliness between groups within the community. Onwunali et al. (2006) also suggested that supply chain public relations help supply chain actors to determine a community's strengths and weaknesses and analyses of its needs and welfare. They further submitted that for an effective supply chain public relation management practice aimed at improving the community the organizations operate

by building a community relation as well as focusing on maintaining the company reputation for good citizenship through social responsibility, economic and environmental sustainability. Okafor and Malizu (2014) upheld that a supply chain public relations practitioner must identify ways of listening to and responding to sensitivity of the local community and extending the facilities of the organization to the said communities as well as provision of social amenities that the community may be in need of. In the assertion of Shamsan and Otieno (2015) the community may be in need of basic amenities such as portable water supply, schools, health facilities to mention but a few, job opportunities, scholarships, vocational training, sponsorship of cultural events and social and recreational activities like sport are not also left out. Community relation is a specialized arm of public relations that focuses on building mutual and profitable relationship between and organization and its host. In order to bridge a gap in knowledge, scholar's empirical investigation is examined below. Onsongo et al. (2017), Shamsan & Otieno (2015) and Okafor & Malizu (2014) suggested that effective and efficient supply chain management practices should include; proper event management, proactive new management, coordinated speeches delivering and good media relationship management. These variables are considered as the dimensions of supply chain public relations management practices to be discussed in the next section. Nevertheless, some scholarly empirical investigations to enable us bridge knowledge gap are explored below.

Okafor and Malizu (2014) investigated the role of public relations in effective organizational management using a systematic literature review to

explain certain key concepts such as organization – public relationships and organizational reputation integrated into a theoretical framework of public relations effectiveness. The findings concluded that when those concepts are integrated in a model, the role of public relations can be captured more clearly than when there is a separate focus on each of the concept. Nyenyeri et al. (2014) investigated the effect of public relations in forestry service delivery at Kenya Forestry Service Headquarters by assessing the effect of public relation in providing information in forestry services. The sampling of 70 respondents was selected through a survey. Interview was scheduled and developed while same was used to collect data from various heads of departments at Kenya Forestry Service Headquarters. The study revealed upon conclusion that public relation has an important role to play in an organization by promoting product image, creating product interest, providing enlightenment and reinforcing brand awareness. Onsongo and Jjuuko (2017) examined the contribution of public relations practice to organizational effectiveness focusing on current execution of public relations activities and how they enhance organizational effectiveness of private universities using a quantitative and descriptive research design. The findings revealed that public relations had a significant impact on organization effectiveness. The study recommended enhancement of public relations practice in private universities to excellency standards of order to facilitate public relations to have a real contribution to effectiveness of the institutions. Shamsan and Otieno (2015) explored the effect of strategic public relations on organization performance using a case study of Red Cross Kenya.

The data were analysed using descriptive statistics and the findings indicated that there is a significant effect of strategic public relations on organization performance. Based on the foregoing empirical investigation, it is clearly seen that these studies did not take into consideration the performance improvement of supply chain public relations management practices on small and medium scale enterprises. On the basis of this limitation, the current study sought to investigate the effect of supply chain public relations management practices on small and medium scale enterprises in Calabar, Cross River state thereby bridging a gap in knowledge. The next section will discuss supply chain public relations management practices to enable the researchers developed research hypotheses.

2.1 Supply Chain Events Management

Supply chain public relations managers use event such as news conferences, seminars, outings exhibit and anniversaries to reach the target public. For example, Ragolis Water Limited used the occasion of customer forum to sensitize its customers and public about its repositioned product (Olayika and Aminu 2006). According to (Esu, 2005), events are occasions or activities organized by the company to capture the attention and interest of its public. These include, seminars, facility tours, exhibition, contest and competitions anniversaries sport and culture sponsorship. Kotler and keller (2013) explained further that companies can draw attention to new products or other company activities by arranging and publicizing special event such as news conference, seminars, outing, trade show exhibits, contest and competitions, and anniversaries that will reach the target public. Dibbm Simkin Pride and Ferrell (2006)

described public relations events as one short ad hoc affair concerned with a specific purpose such as an open day or VIP visit. On the basis of the foregoing argument, the following hypothesis is formulated:

Ho₁: supply chain event management has no effect on business performance of small and medium scale enterprises in Calabar.

2.2 Supply Chain News Management

Supply chain public relations professionals create favourable news about their organization, product and people. For instance, Olayika and Aminu (2005) and Mpuon et al. (2022b) argued that Globacom made so much news when it was recruiting and importing equipment and machinery, raising the expectation of the public to be imminent launching of its network. Also, Kotler and Kelle (2013) and Mpuon et al. (2022a) further stated that one of the major tasks of supply chain public relations professionals is to find and create favourable news about the company's products, services and also encourage the media to accept press release and attend press conference. Public relations expert creates favourable news about the company's and product, news generated by the company's public relation department is referred to as a press release (Esu 2005). Based on the discussion above, the following hypothesis is put forward for testing:

Ho₂: Supply chain news management has no effect on business performance of SMSEs in Calabar

2.3 Supply Chain Speeches Management

Supply chain speeches by the company's managing director, executive directors, top management staff and supply chain public relations practitioners help boost the organization's public image. Adrain Wood, Former Manging Director MTN and Afam Edom

Chief Marketing Officer, were always at one occasion or the other to deliver speeches that enhanced organization performance (Olayika & Aminu, 2006). According to Esu (2005) supply chain speeches presented by a company spokesman about the company's activities are effective supply chain public relations tool that enables the firms to boost their image and reputation. Onsongo et al (2017) and Mpuon (2019, 2018a, 2018b) argued that such speeches may be presented during trade association or sales meeting or at a media forum. Furthermore, Kotler & Keller (2013) and Mpuon & Oyong (2021) opined that I encourage supply chain speeches management company executives must field questions from the media or organize talks at trade association or sales meetings and these appearances can build the company's image. According to Kotler and Keller (2013) Companies can build supply chain goodwill that help in contributing money and time to good causes and strengthening public service activities through good speeches that enhance social responsibilities undertaken by corporate manager to improve the company's image and reputation and also support community affairs like building of schools, provision of electricity and award of scholarship (Esu, 2005). According to Olayika and Aminu (2006) good supply chain speeches enables companies to build goodwill by making donations either in cash or in kind to good cause by attracting supply chain participants to donate relief materials and emergency rescue operations during emergency period as a way of improving their business performance and building goodwill. Following the deliberation above, we hypothesized as follows:

Ho₃: Supply chain speeches management has no effect on business performance of SMSEs in Calabar.

2.4 Supply Chain Media Relation

Supply chain media relation has tremendously affected the productivity of SMSEs in Calabar.

Media relation report carried out by both electronic and supply chain print media managers about SMSEs business performance in Calabar has built a good image and reputation regarding their services and products in the mind of prospective customers of the companies and also consolidated their goodwill. Supply chain media relation have tremendous effects on business performance of SMEs enterprises in Calabar (Nwodu et al, 2014). Reports carried out by both supply chain electronic and print media demonstrated that supply chain media relations strengthened customer relationship management that encourages mutual relationships among supply chain participants. Supply chain media relation help in building a good image and reputation about the company in the minds of perspective customers of the company which has also consolidated the goodwill that customers of the company already held about the company's performance. Supply chain media relation is an essential aspect of supply chain public relations management practices (Onabajo, 2005). In the light of the foregoing argument, we theorized as follows:

Ho₄: supply chain media relations have no effect on business performance of SMSEs in Calabar.

2.5 Theoretical Framework

This research will be based on two theories, the agenda setting and priming theories of media. These theories are presented as follows

2.6 Priming Theory

Priming theory is defined by McQuail (2005) as "the activity of the media in proposing the values and standards by which objects of media attention can be judged". However, Miller (2005) refers of priming as "the effects of a prior context on retrieval and

interpretation of information. The media's content will provide a lot of time and space to certain supply issues, making these issues more accessible and vivid in the public's mind. Priming tells the audience whether the news item is good or bad and whether it is communicated effectively. For example, if a supply chain news item is very important, it will always be given much attention like being placed on the first page, it is given a lot of space and the pictures can be printed in different colours. This will attract the attention of the audience (reader). If media portrays this issue of drug abuse as bad, then that is how the audience will receive the news and for this reason we find in most cases media influence negatively or positively how the audience perceived things most especially supply chain activities

3.0 METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a quantitative cross-sectional survey of two hundred and fifty small and medium scale enterprises using judgement sampling techniques to achieve the research objectives. This design was selected because the researchers made no effort to control extraneous variables as obtainable in experimental research. The sampling structure of the study included all small and medium scale enterprises quoted with Nigeria's stock exchange or registered with Nigeria's

Corporate Affairs Commission formed in 1990 on the basis of Allied Matters Act No 1 1990 as amended. The sample size is composed of 500 explicitly selected management staff from the 250 small and medium enterprises surveyed. Two questionnaires were given to the management staff of each of the 250 small and medium scale enterprises.

The instrument tagged supply chain public relations management practices and business performance questionnaire (SCPRMPBPQ) was used in data collection. The instrument was divided into three sections, section A, B and C. Section A comprises of three items on the demographics of the respondents

(gender, education qualifications and years of experience) section B comprises of 20 items on –the independent variable (supply chain public relations management practices) with 10 items on social sustainability and environmental sustainability respectively. Section C comprises of 5 items on dependent variable (business performance). All items on the instrument excluding the demographics of the respondents were rated on five points scale of strongly agree, agree, disagree. Strongly disagree and neutral which were scored 4, 3, 2, 1, and 0 respectively. The instrument was validated by two experts in management and one expert in test and measurements from the University of Uyo. The reliability of the instrument was administered to 30 employees of small and medium scale enterprises who are part of the main population but do not take part in the main study. The reliability coefficients of 0.743, 0.7052, 0.722, 0.744 and 0.842 for supply chain event management, supply chain news management, supply chain speeches management, supply chain media relations and business performance respectively. Based on these reliability coefficients, the instrument was adjusted reliable. Frequency, percentage and multiple regression were used to analyses the data and was facilitated using the statistical package for social sciences (SPSS version 22.0).

To collect the appropriate data, a hybrid of site visit and structured questionnaire was used. A total of 500 questionnaires were given to the employees of the purposely selected small and medium scale enterprises. The definition of the questionnaire to be administered was built on the basis of the quality of the research hypotheses. The questionnaires were checked at the firms on the informant to ensure material consistency, accuracy and ease of use. The respondents were known in their different companies by their classification/explicit obligations. The study purpose was clarified to the respondents and they were also given written guarantee of anonymity and

confidentiality of answers (in the form of cover letters). The data was obtained in two steps. First, the group's business development managers were interviewed structurally because their impression correctly defined the firm's position based on their higher level and knowledge of the firm which was used to elicit the global views of the senior management and core issues with respect to supply chain public relations management practices.

Following regular visits and reminders (using telephone calls and text message) to participants at organizational level such as line managers, 465 completed questionnaires, showing a response rate of 93% were retrieved. 74 questionnaires were considered unsuitable for conclusion in the analysis after testing for completeness of the responses, resulting in a modified sample size of 391.

4.0 RESULTS Table 1: Demographics of the Respondents

Demographics Variables	No. Of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Male	270	69.1
Female	121	30.9
Total	391	100.0
Age (years)		
20-25 years	130	33.2
26-30 years	64	16.4
31-35 years	58	14.8
36-40 years	27	6.9
41-45 years	51	13.0
46-50	27	6.9
51 and above	34	8.7
Total	391	100.0
Educational Qualification		
None	9	2.3
Primary	78	19.9
Secondary	126	32.2
Tertiary	178	45.5
Total	391	100.0
Marital status		
Married	115	29.4
Single	197	50.4
Widow	40	10.2
Divorced	14	3.6
Separated	25	6.4
Total	391	100.0

Experience		
1- 5 years	95	24.3
6-10 years	154	39.4
11-15 years	83	21.2
Above 15 years	59	15.1
Total	391	100.0

Of the 500 copies of the questionnaire administered, 391 copies representing 78.2% of the total number of the questionnaire were retrieved and found useable. Results presented in Table 4.1 shows the distribution of the demographics of the respondents. Result reveals that 270 respondents representing 69.1% of the respondents were male and 121 respondents representing 30.9% were female. The distribution of their age shows that 33.2% were between 20-25 years, 16.4% were between 26-30 years, 14.8% were between 31-35 years while 6.9%, 13.0%, 6.9% and 8.7% of the respondents were between 31-35 years, 36-40 years, 41-45 years and 51 and above years

respectively. Nine respondents representing 2.3% had no formal education, 19.9% had primary education, 32.2% had secondary education while the majority of the respondents (45.5%) had tertiary education. One hundred and fifteen respondents representing 29.4% were married, 50.4% were single, 10.2% were widow, 3.6% were divorced while 6.4% of the respondents were separated. Result of the years of experience shows that 24.3% of the respondents had 1-5 years, 39.4% had 6-10 years, 21.2% had 11-15years while 15.1% of the respondents had above 15 years of experience.

Table 2: Descriptive statistics for the research variables

	n	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness		Kurtosis	
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
SC event MGT	391	10.00	40.00	28.48	11.60	-0.56	0.12	-1.42	0.25
SC news MGT	391	9.00	36.00	25.73	10.79	-0.65	0.12	-1.47	0.25
SC speech MGT	391	8.00	58.00	21.71	9.27	1.64	0.123	5.02	0.25
SC media relations	391	7.00	28.00	18.93	6.54	-0.22	0.12	-1.05	0.25

Business performance	391	4.00	16.00	11.48	5.28	-0.51	0.12	-1.61	0.25
Valid N (listwise)	391								

Source: Researchers Computation with SPSS 20

Table 4.2 presents the summary results of the descriptive statistics for the research variables. Table 4.2 presents the minimum score, maximum score, mean and standard deviation, skewness and kurtosis of the scores obtained on each of the research variable. Result shows that the mean score of 28.48, 25.73, 21.71, 18.93 and 11.48 for SC event management, SC news management, SC speeches management, SC media relation and business performance with standard deviations of 11.60, 10.79, 9.27, 6.54 and 5.28 respectively. In terms of skewness, result shows that the scores obtained for SC event management (-0.56), SC news management (-0.56), speeches management (-0.22) and media relation (-0.51) were less than 1 meaning that they are skewed to the left

while that obtained for business performance was greater than 1 (1.64) meaning that the scores on business performance was skewed to the right. Result also shows that the kurtosis for SC event management (-1.42), news management (-1.47), speeches management (-1.05) media relation (-1.61) were less than 3.00 while that of business performance (5.02) was greater than 3.00 which is the kurtosis of the normal distribution. This result indicates that among the research variables, only business performance has higher kurtosis than normal distribution suggesting that the scores obtained on business performance is leptokurtic (excess kurtosis). The normality of the scores obtained on each of the variables using Shapiro-Wilks test are presented in Table 4.3.

Table 3: Summary of Normality Test using Shapiro-Wilk test for the Research Variables

Shapiro-Wilk

	Statistic	df	P-value
SC event management	0.801	391	0.000
SC news management	0.732	391	0.000
SC speeches management	0.857	391	0.000
SC media relation	0.927	391	0.000
Business performance	0.718	391	0.000

Source: Author's computation (2019) using SPSS version 20.0

Result displayed in Table 4.3 reveals that SC event management (P-value = 0.000), SC news management (P-value = 0.000), SC speeches

management (P-value = 0.000), SC media relation (P-value = 0.000) and business performance (P-value = 0.000) have their P-values less than 0.05 ($P < 0.05$).

Table 4: Correlation between the research variables

Variables	1	2	3	4	5
1. SC event MGT	1				
1. SC news MGT	0.807** (0.000)	1			
2. SC speeches MGT	0.548** (0.000)	0.699** (0.000)	1		
3. SC media relations	0.543** (0.000)	0.589** (0.000)	0.813** (0.000)	1	
4. Business performance	0.650** (0.000)	0.611** (0.000)	0.602** (0.000)	0.705** (0.000)	1

**Significant at 5% ($p < 0.05$), **significant at 1% ($p < 0.01$), Source: Author's computation (2019) using SPSS version 20.0. Values in the parentheses are the p-values.*

Result in Table 4.4 presents the correlation between the research variables. Result reveals that SC event management has a significant positive relationship with SC news management ($r = 0.807$, $p = 0.000$, $p < 0.01$), SC speeches management ($r = 0.548$, $p = 0.000$, $p < 0.01$), SC media relations ($r = 0.543$, $p = 0.000$, $p < 0.01$) and business performance ($r = 0.650$, $p = 0.000$, $p < 0.01$). SC event management was found to have significant positive relationship with SC news management ($r = 0.699$, $p = 0.000$, $p < 0.01$), SC

This indicates that among the research variables, all the research variables were not normally distributed.

speeches management ($r = 0.589$, $p = 0.000$, $p < 0.01$) and SC media relations ($r = 0.611$, $p = 0.000$, $p < 0.01$). Business performance shows significant positive relationship with SC event management ($r = 0.813$, $p = 0.000$, $p < 0.01$) and SC media relations ($r = 0.602$, $p = 0.000$, $p < 0.01$). There was also a significant positive relationship between business performance and SC speeches management ($r = 0.705$, $p = 0.000$, $p < 0.01$).

4.1 Test of Hypotheses Hypothesis 1

H_{01} : There is no positive significant relationship between SC event management and business performance.

Table .5: Model summary for the regression relationship between SC event management and business performance

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R Std. Error of the Estimate	of the Durbin-Watson
	.582	.338	.337	7.54869	2.835

Source: Researchers Computation with SPSS 20.

Result in Table 4.5 shows r- square of 0.338 which means that 33.8 percent of the variation in business performance was accounted for by SC event management. This result also signifies that if there is any improvement in SC event management, there will be a corresponding improvement in business performance. The Durbin Watson value of 2.835 was obtained which implies that there is no evidence of autocorrelation. This is because The Durbin Watson

value of 2.835 is greater than 1 but less than 3.00 which indicate that the error terms are not correlated as suggested by Field (Field, 2009). The result of the Analysis of Variance for the regression is shown in Table 4.6.

Table 6: ANOVA Result for the relationship between SC event management and business performance

Source of variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-calc.	F-crit.	p-value
Regression	11339.645	1	11339.645	199.002	3.87	0.000
Residual	22166.273	389	56.983			
Total	33505.918	390				

***Significant at $p < 0.05$. Source: Researchers Computation with SPSS 20.**

From Table 4.6, the F-critical of 199.002 was obtained with p-value of 0.000 while the F- critical of 3.87 at the 0.05 level of significance. The result reveals that the F-calculated (199.002) is greater than the F-

critical (3.87) at the 0.05 level of significances which means that there is a significant linear relationship between SC event management and business performance. This result also implies that the SC event management accounted for significant variation in businesses performance. The estimate of the

parameters of the regression model is shown in Table 4.7.

Table 7: Parameters estimates of the regression of business performance on SC event management

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		t-calc.	P-value
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
Constant	8.480	1.013			8.373	0.000**
SC management event	0.465	0.033	0.582		14.107	0.000**

****Significant at 1 % (p<0.01), t-critical = 1.97.**

Source: Researchers Computation with SPSS 20.

Table 4.5 presents the regression coefficient for the model parameters. Result shows that SC event management ($\beta = 0.582$, S.E = 0.033, t-calc. = 14.107, t-crit. = 1.97, p = 0.000, p < 0.05) has significant positive relationship with business performance. Result also yielded standardized beta coefficient of 0.582 was obtained which indicates that if other variables are held constant, for every 1 unit improvement in SC event management, business performance will improve by 0.582. Result also

shows that t-calculated (14.107) is greater than the t-critical (1.97) at the 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis stated above is rejected. Therefore, there is a significant positive relationship between SC event management and business performance. This result indicates that effective SC event management enhances business performance.

4.2 Hypothesis 2

Ho₂: There is no positive significant relationship between SC news management and business performance.

Table 8: Model summary for the regression relationship between SC news management and business performance

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R Std. Error of the Estimate	of the Durbin-Watson
	.723	.523	.522	4.52267	2.337

Source: Researchers Computation with SPSS 20.

Result in Table 4.8 reveals r-square of 0.523 which implies that 52.3 percent of the variation in business

performance was accounted for by SC news management. This result also signifies that if there is any improvement in SC news management, there will

be a corresponding improvement in business performance. The Durbin Watson value of 2.337 was obtained which implies that there is no evidence of autocorrelation. This is because The Durbin Watson value of 2.337 is greater than 1 but less than 3.00

which indicate that the error terms are not correlated as suggested by Field (Field, 2009). The result of the Analysis of Variance for the regression is shown in Table 4.9.

Table 9: ANOVA Result for the relationship between SC news management and business performance

Source of variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-calc.	F-crit.	p-value
Regression	8725.189	1	8725.189	426.565*	3.87	0.000
Residual	7956.806	389	20.455			
Total	16681.995	390				

***Significant at $p < 0.05$. Source: Researchers Computation with SPSS 20.**

From Table 4.9, the F-critical of 426.565 was obtained with p-value of 0.000 while the F-critical of 3.87 at the 0.05 level of significance. The result reveals that the F-calculated (426.565) is greater than the F-critical (3.87) at the 0.05 level of significances which

means that there is a significant linear relationship between SC news management and business performance. This result also implies that the SC news management accounted for significant variation in business performance. The estimate of the parameters of the regression model is shown in Table 4.10.

Table 10: Parameters estimates of the regression of business performance on SC news management

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		t-calc.	P-value
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
Constant	7.320	.607			12.064	0.000*
SC management news	.408	.020	.723		20.653	0.000*

***Significant at 1 % ($p < 0.01$), t-critical = 1.97. Source: Researchers Computation with SPSS 20.**

Table 4.10 presents the regression coefficient for the model parameters. Result shows that SC news management ($\beta = 0.723$, S.E = 0.020, t-calc. = 20.653, t-crit. = 1.97, $p = 0.000$, $p < 0.05$) has significant positive

relationship business performance. Result also yielded standardized beta coefficient of 0.723 was obtained which indicates that if other variables are held constant, for every 1-unit improvement in SC news management, business performance will

improve by 0.723. Result also shows that t-calculated (20.653) is greater than the t-critical (1.97) at the 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis stated above is rejected. Therefore, there is a significant positive relationship between SC news management and business performance. This result indicates that

Table 11: Model summary for the regression relationship between SC speeches management and business performance

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R Std. Error of the Estimate	of the Durbin-Watson
	.624	.389	.387	7.25442	2.838

Source: Researchers Computation with SPSS 20.

Result in Table 4.11 reveals r-square of 0.389 which implies that 38.9 percent of the variation in business performance was accounted for by SC speeches management. This result also signifies that if there is any improvement in SC speeches management, there will be a corresponding improvement in business

effective SC news management enhances business performance.

4.3 Hypothesis 3

H₀₃: There is no positive significant relationship between SC speeches management and business performance.

performance. The Durbin Watson value of 2.838 was obtained which implies that there is no evidence of autocorrelation. This is because The Durbin Watson value of 2.838 is greater than 1 but less than 3.00 which indicate that the error terms are not correlated as suggested by Field (Field, 2009). The result of the Analysis of Variance for the regression is shown in Table 4.12.

Table 12: ANOVA Result for the relationship between SC speeches management and business performance

Source of variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-calc.	F-crit.	p-value
Regression	13034.190	1	13034.190	247.673*	3.87	0.000
Residual	20471.728	389	52.627			
Total	33505.918	390				

*

Significant at p<0.05. Source: Researchers Computation with SPSS 20.

From Table 4.12, the F-critical of 247.673 was obtained with p-value of 0.000 while the F-critical of 3.87 at the 0.05 level of significance. The result reveals that the F-calculated (247.673) is greater than the F-critical (3.87) at the 0.05 level of significances

which means that there is a significant linear relationship between SC speeches management and business performance. This result also implies that the SC speeches management accounted for significant variation in business performance. The estimate of the parameters of the regression model is shown in Table 4.13.

Table 13: Parameters estimates of the regression of business performance on SC speeches management

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Std. Error	Standardized Coefficients Beta	t-calc.	P-value
	B					
Constant	7.929	.950			8.349	0.000*
SC speeches management	0.536	0.034	0.624		15.738	0.000*

***significant at 1 % ($p < 0.01$), t-critical = 1.97.**

Source: Researchers Computation with SPSS 20.

Table 4.13 presents the regression coefficient for the model parameters. Result shows that SC speeches management ($\beta = 0.624$, S.E = 0.034, t-calc. = 15.738, t-crit. = 1.97, $p = 0.000$, $p < 0.05$) has significant positive relationship with business performance. Result also yielded standardized beta coefficient of 0.624 was obtained which indicates that if other variables are held constant, for every 1-unit improvement in SC speeches management, business performance will improve by 0.624. Result also shows that t-calculated

(15.738) is greater than the t-critical (1.97) at the 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis stated above is rejected. Therefore, there is a significant positive relationship between SC speeches management and business performance. This result indicates that effective SC speeches management enhanced business performance.

4.4 Hypothesis 4

Ho4: There is no positive significant relationship between SC media relations and business performance

Table.14: Model summary for the regression relationship between SC media relations and business performance

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R Std. Error of the Estimate	of the Durbin-Watson
	.765	.586	.585	4.21465	2.250

Source: Researchers Computation with SPSS 20.

Result in Table 4.14 reveals r- square of 0.586 which implies that 58.6 percent of the variation in profitability was accounted for by SC media relations. This result also signifies that if there is any

improvement in SC media relations, there will be a corresponding improvement in business performance. The Durbin Watson value of 2.250 was obtained which implies that there is no evidence of autocorrelation. This is because The Durbin Watson

value of 2.250 is greater than 1 but less than 3.00 which indicate that the error terms are not correlated as suggested by Field (Field, 2009). The result of the

Analysis of Variance for the regression is shown in Table 4.15.

Table 15: ANOVA Result for the relationship between SC media relations and business performance

Source of variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-calc.	F-crit.	p-value
Regression	9772.070	1	9772.070	550.127*	3.87	0.000
Residual	6909.925	389	17.763			
Total	16681.995	390				

***Significant at $p < 0.05$. Source: Researchers Computation with SPSS 20.**

From Table 4.15, the F-critical of 550.127 was obtained with p-value of 0.000 while the F-critical of 3.87 at the 0.05 level of significance. The result reveals that the F-calculated (550.127) is greater than the F-critical (3.87) at the 0.05 level of significances

which means that there is a significant linear relationship between SC media relations and business performance. This result also implies that SC media relations accounted for significant variation in business performance. The estimate of the parameters of the regression model is shown in

Table 16: Parameters estimates of the regression of business performance on SC media relation

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t-calc.	P-value
Constant	6.992	.552		12.674	0.000*
SC media relation	.464	0.020	0.765	23.455	0.000*

***significant at 1 % ($p < 0.01$), t-critical = 1.97. Source: Researchers Computation with SPSS 20.**

Table 4.16 presents the regression coefficient for the model parameters. Result shows that SC media relation ($\beta = 0.765$, S. E= 0.020, t-calc. = 23.455, t-crit. = 1.97, $p = 0.000$, $p < 0.05$) has significant positive relationship with business performance. Result also yielded standardized beta coefficient of 0.765 was

obtained which indicates that if other variables are held constant, for every 1-unit improvement in SC media relation, business performance will improve by 0.765. Result also shows that t-calculated (23.455) is greater than the t-critical (1.97) at the 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis stated above is rejected. Therefore, there is a significant positive relationship between SC media relations and business

performance. This result indicates that effective SC media relation enhances business performance.

5.0 DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

The findings demonstrated that supply chain public relations management practices dimensions had a considerable favourable effect on business performance of small and medium scale enterprises in Calabar. This could be because small and medium scale enterprises collaborate with upstream and downstream supply chain participants such as suppliers, manufacturers, intermediaries and customers to enhance their business performance by integrating public relations management practices into their supply chain performance. Specifically, the findings revealed that supply chain event management, news practice, speeches management and media relations technique have a significant positive impact on business performance of small and medium scale enterprises in Nigeria.

6.0 CONCLUSION

AND

RECOMMENDATIONS

The study demonstrated beyond all reasonable doubts that most of the organization in Nigeria that have escaped distress and liquidation have placed greater premium on supply chain public relations management practices as mechanisms for staying afloat in restoring confidence in their customers and

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business performance. In conclusion, the findings from the study revealed that small and medium scale enterprises will enhance trust and confidence to their customers and other institutions using supply chain public relations management practices dimensions such as media service, news and event management to achieve business performance. Based on the findings from the study, the following recommendations are put forward

1. Small and medium scale enterprises should do everything possible to promote supply chain event management as a dimensions public relations management practice to enhance their business performance in terms of customer service, profitability and brand image.
2. Small and medium scale enterprises should adopt effective supply chain news management strategies to boost their public image and improve on the relationship with other key institutions.
3. Effective and efficient speeches management techniques should be implemented by small and medium scale enterprises to improve on their business performance.
4. Small and medium scale enterprises should adopt good supply chain media relations techniques to create mutual relationship and commitment between supply chain participants.

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